

1 **Submerged macrophytes in Danish lakes: impact of morphological and chemical factors on abundance**
2 **and species richness**

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13

14 **Abstract**

15 We analysed long-term monitoring data on submerged macrophytes and water chemistry from 666 Danish
16 lakes >1 hectare and mean depth < 3 m, encompassing a total of 1447 lake years. Our aim was to describe
17 how plant cover (COV), plant volume inhabited (PVI) and species richness related to physical and chemical
18 and environmental variables. Boosted regression tree analyses revealed that chlorophyll *a*, Secchi depth
19 and depth were the strongest predictors of COV and PVI. Chlorophyll had a strong negative effect up to 50
20 µg/l, whereas the changes related to Secchi depth and depth were more gradual and covered more of the
21 gradient. Macrophyte species richness was best predicted by lake area and alkalinity, with chlorophyll *a*,
22 nutrients and colour having significant but less marked effects. For chlorophyll *a*, 78% of the observed
23 variance could be explained by the BRT model, with the most powerful predictors being both phosphorus,
24 and nitrogen, but with significant additional effects of plant cover and alkalinity. Our analyses revealed
25 limited direct effect of nutrients on macrophyte abundance but an indirect hierarchical effect of nutrients
26 mediated through chlorophyll *a* with additional interactive effects by plant cover itself, alkalinity, mean
27 depth and colour.

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34 phosphorus, nutrients

35

36

37 **Introduction**

38 For decades, human activities and increased eutrophication have resulted in higher turbidity and a
39 decrease or even loss of submerged macrophytes in lakes all over the world (Sayer et al., 2010; Phillips et
40 al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2017; Stefanidis et al., 2019). Following external nutrient loading reduction, lake
41 recovery with re-establishment of submerged macrophytes is a key target, particularly in shallow lakes
42 where submerged macrophytes may help to ensure clear water conditions due to several positive feedback
43 mechanisms (Scheffer et al., 1993; Li et al., 2000; Kosten et al., 2009). Submerged macrophytes are also
44 important for the overall biodiversity, as many fish, invertebrates, attached algae and microorganisms are
45 associated with the plants (Declerck et al., 2005; Bolduc et al., 2016). Additionally, submerged macrophytes
46 play a significant role for lake managers, as their sensitivity to eutrophication makes them useful indicators
47 of ecological status (Søndergaard et al., 2010; Kolada et al., 2014; Verhofstad & Bakker, 2019). Accordingly,
48 in EU's Water Framework Directive macrophytes are one of the four biological elements that are used to
49 define whether measures should be taken to reduce the external loading of nutrients to lakes in order to
50 improve their status (Poikane et al., 2018).

51
52 Submerged macrophytes represent a diverse group of organisms, and they contribute to a number of
53 vegetation-turbidity feedback mechanisms (Jeppesen et al., 1998; Hilt et al., 2018; Ersoy et al., 2020).
54 Macrophytes interact with, for instance, fish and macroinvertebrates (Schultz & Dibble, 2012), waterbirds
55 (Larson et al., 2020), zooplankton (Burks et al., 2001) and phytoplankton (Sayer et al., 2010), and they affect
56 the food chain length, ecosystem function (Ziegler et al., 2015), biogeochemical processes, such as the
57 redox potential around the sediment-water interface (Boros et al., 2011), as well as methane emissions
58 (Sorrell et al., 2002). Thus, besides being affected by nutrient loading-induced changes in turbidity,
59 submerged macrophytes also respond to and depend on a number of biological interactions. Spatial and
60 temporal variability in macrophyte abundance is often high and large differences in macrophyte
61 communities occur, even under relatively comparable environmental conditions (Gillard et al., 2020; Yang
62 et al., 2020). The mechanisms behind this variability are not always clear but may, among other factors, be
63 induced by yearly climatic variations or a delayed response to changed environmental conditions (Jeppesen
64 et al., 2005; Ejankowski & Lenard, 2015; Sand-Jensen et al., 2017).

65
66 Here, we used a data set from 666 Danish lakes covering a large gradient in morphological and chemical
67 characteristics and including data on submerged macrophyte composition and abundance. The lakes
68 comprise lowland, temperate, shallow and meso- to hypertrophic lakes where submerged macrophytes can
69 be both very abundant and very sparse. Our aim was to examine how the direct and indirect effects of lake
70 morphometry and nutrients shape three central aspects of submerged macrophytes – cover, plant volume
71 inhabited and species number – with the aim to better identify the factors structuring the submerged
72 macrophyte community in shallow lakes along a gradient of morphological and chemical factors.

73
74 **Methods and data**

75 Sampling and lake characteristics

76 Chemical and biological data were collected by regional and national authorities as part of the nationwide
77 Danish monitoring program on the aquatic environment, NOVANA, running since 1989 with the inclusion of
78 macrophytes in 1993. According to the program, physical and chemical variables are sampled using well-
79 defined and comparable techniques and analytical procedures (Svendsen et al., 2005). The physical data
80 include lake area, mean water depth and Secchi depth, and the chemical data encompass total nitrogen
81 (TN), total phosphorus (TP), total alkalinity (TA) and chlorophyll *a* (Chl_a). Each lake is sampled from one
82 location from the deepest part of the lake at least four times during summer, and mean summer (1 May to
83 30 September) concentrations are calculated. See Søndergaard et al. (2005) for more detailed descriptions.

84
85 A total of 666 lakes with an area > 1 ha and a mean depth < 3 m were included in the data analyses. About
86 half of these lakes (338 lakes) were visited twice or several times during the monitoring period (25 years),

87 which increased the total dataset to 1447 lake years. Most of the lakes sampled multiple times were visited
88 with an interval of at least three years, but some of the lakes were included in a more comprehensive
89 sampling program, and nine lakes were thus visited 10-22 times with an interval of 1-3 years. In the
90 analyses and presentations, we used data from all lake years (hereafter mainly referred to as “lakes”).
91

92 Submerged macrophytes were monitored during their maximum abundance between 1 July and 15 August.
93 In each lake 30-375 observation points located along a number of transects in each lake where numbers
94 were lake size dependent. All lakes > 5 ha had at least 150 sampling points. The transects covered the
95 whole lake area and all depth zones which potentially could sustain the growth of macrophytes. The
96 number of transects were adjusted according to the shape of the lake in order to give an overall description
97 of the whole lake area. At each sampling point, water depth, species presence, total coverage of
98 submerged species and mean plant height were estimated using either a water glass or a rake or by a diver
99 in deep lakes. Macrophyte coverage was estimated using a scale from 0 to 6 representing: 0% (no plants),
100 0-5%, 6-25%, 26-50%, 51-75%, 76-95% and 96-100%. For each lake year, mean macrophyte coverage (COV,
101 %) was calculated based on how large a depth zone and area each sampling point represented relative to
102 the whole lake area. The proportionate mean plant volume inhabited (PVI, %) at each sampling point was
103 calculated as: $PVI = COV * \text{mean plant height} / \text{water depth}$. The calculation of COV and PVI did not include
104 filamentous algae or floating-leaved species. A total taxa list and taxa number were obtained from transect
105 observations supplemented with additional observations of extra taxa in selected areas. Macrophyte taxa
106 included floating-leaved species of which submerged forms were observed.
107

108 The lakes cover large gradients in morphological and chemical characteristics, but most are small (median
109 area = 15 ha), shallow (median mean depth = 1.1 m), non-humic (median colour = 38 mg Pt/l), freshwater
110 (median conductivity = 42 mS/m) and eutrophic (median Chla = 40 µg/l and median TP = 0.112 mg/l) (Table
111 1). Median COV was 11%, median PVI 3% and median taxa number five. Submerged macrophytes were
112 absent in 11.6% of the lakes and in 13.2% of the observed lake years.
113

114 Data analyses

115 Analyses were performed using boosted regression tree analysis (BRT) (Elith et al., 2008; Beaulieu et al.,
116 2020, Jarvis et al., 2020), which is a machine learning technique that tests for relationships between
117 predictors (in this case physical and chemical variables, see Table 1) and response variables (here three
118 macrophyte indicators in shallow lakes and Chla) in a dataset. The principle is that a second model is
119 “boosted” from the previous one by minimising its errors in order to achieve the best new model derived
120 through a model simplification process, where each predictor is left out sequentially and the reduction in
121 the predictive power is used to determine if it should stay in or not. The method can deal with highly
122 collinear data and provides a good estimate of the relative influence of each predictor and the shape of the
123 relationship between predictor and response variable. The outcome of the BRT analyses is presented as
124 partial dependency plots that show the pattern between the predictor and the response independent of all
125 the other predictors. The predictive power is represented by the total variance explained together with the
126 relative importance of the most important explanatory variables. In this study, BRT analyses were used to
127 test the influence of environmental factors on three main macrophyte indicators: COV, PVI and taxa
128 number. A BRT analysis was also conducted for Chla because of its strong impact on all macrophyte
129 indicators (see for example Søndergaard et al., 2010). A few extreme outliers with Chla above 1000 µg/l
130 and TA above 10 meq/l were removed prior to the analyses. The analyses were conducted on the whole
131 data set as well as a subset of lakes with TP < 2 mg/l (when analysing Chla) and Chla < 200 µg/l (when
132 analysing COV) in order to avoid extreme high values of TP and Chla.
133

134 The BRT analysis was carried out following the guidelines of Elith et al. (2008); tree complexity and learning
135 rate were set so as to ensure at least 5000 trees in the analysis. Tree complexity was set at three with a
136 learning rate of 0.005 and with the bag fraction set at 0.75, and only results from the simplified trees are

137 presented. A cost-complexity measure was used to eliminate non-influential predictors by sequentially
138 dropping the least important each variable and assessing the loss in predictive power, no more predictors
139 were dropped if there was a loss in predictive power larger than a standard error of the original model. The
140 predictors that are retained in the simplified model can therefore be thought of as significant predictors.
141 Partial dependence plots of fitted function versus observed values for variables significantly predicting the
142 response variables were prepared; these seek to present the influence uniquely attributable to a single
143 predictor. BRT analysis was carried out using gbm package (Greenwell et al., 2018) with additional code
144 from Elith et al. (2008), and standard regression trees were constructed using the rpart package (Therneau
145 et al., 2019), using R v. 4.0.2 (R Core Team, 2020).

146
147 We also conducted multiple regression analyses between taxa number, COV and PVI as dependent
148 variables and \log_{10} of the variables mentioned in Table 1 using SAS PROC REG with forward selection and p-
149 value correction. The multiple regression was first run on all the variables shown in Table 1 and then, in a
150 second step, conducted only for the variables where the partial R^2 was > 0.01 .

151
152 As phosphorus regulation often is used by lake managers to improve lake water quality, sometimes as the
153 only measure (e.g. in Denmark), we also specifically addressed the relationship between TP and COV. The
154 frequency distribution of lakes with COV $> 1\%$ and lakes with COV $> 20\%$ was ordered along a TP gradient.
155 Lakes with COV $< 1\%$ was used to represent lakes with no or very low macrophyte cover, lakes with COV $>$
156 1% to represent lakes with the presence macrophytes, and lakes with COV $> 20\%$ to represent shallow lakes
157 where submerged macrophytes are abundant and considered to have a significant impact on the overall
158 biological structure in Danish lakes (Søndergaard et al., 2016). In lakes with high TP (> 0.2 mg/l), differences
159 in environmental factors in lakes with high COV ($> 20\%$) or low COV ($< 1\%$) were tested using the SAS PROC
160 TTEST.

161 162 **Results**

163 BRT and regression analyses

164 The total variance explained by the BRT analyses for the three macrophyte indicators relevant for shallow
165 lakes ranged from 50% for PVI, 62% for COV to 76% for taxa number (Fig. 1). The relative importance of the
166 predictor variables differed, Chla was most important for COV (36%) and PVI (34%), while lake area was
167 most important for taxa number (32%). For COV and in particular PVI, Secchi depth and mean depth were
168 almost as important as Chla, while the second-most important predictor for species richness was alkalinity
169 (24%). For Chla, 78% of the variance was explained using the predictors in Table 1 (not including the three
170 macrophyte indicators). TP was the most important predictor with a relative importance of 38%, followed
171 by TN with 30% and COV with 14%. Restricting the analyses to TP < 2 mg/l for Chla and to Chla < 200 $\mu\text{g/l}$
172 for COV increased the total variance explained to 63% and 80%, respectively (Fig. 2).

173
174 The BRT plots also illustrate the changes in importance along a gradient of the different predictors (Figures
175 1 and 2). For taxa number, lake area was especially important up to ca. 100 ha, but above 500 ha there was
176 no further effect of area. For TA, the second-most important predictor for taxa number, an optimum
177 appeared around an alkalinity of 1 meq/l. For COV, there was a strong effect of Chla up to about 50 $\mu\text{g/l}$ but
178 none at higher concentrations, while the effect of Secchi depth continued up to 4 m. For PVI, the response
179 to increasing Chla was similar to that of COV. A sharp decline in the fitted function for mean depth was
180 seen up to ca. 1.5 m. For Chla, the fitted function increased up to a TP of ca. < 0.2 mg/l, with a relatively
181 short range up to 0.1 mg/l being the most important, whereas TN had a more gradual impact up to about 7
182 mg/l. COV was the third-most important predictor with a relative importance of 13%, and the fitted
183 function particularly decreased up to a COV of 30-40%, after which higher COV had little effect on the fitted
184 function.

185

186 In the multiple regressions using the four macrophyte indicators as dependent variables and \log_{10}
187 transformed environmental variables from Table 1 as predictors, the highest model R^2 was obtained for
188 taxa number ($R^2 = 0.36$) and the lowest for PVI ($R^2 = 0.22$) (Table 2). For COV and PVI, the highest partial R^2
189 was obtained for Chla, while area had the highest partial R^2 for taxa number and Secchi depth the highest
190 R^2 for C_{max} . The parameter estimate for Chla was negative for all macrophyte indicators, whereas area and
191 Secchi depth were positive. Only for taxa number, partial R^2 was > 0.01 for TP or TN.

192 193 Frequency distribution of low and high COV at increasing TP

194 The number of lakes with COV above 1% or 20% decreased with increasing TP (Fig. 3). The reduction in
195 lakes with COV $> 20\%$ occurred particularly when TP increased from < 10 to 40-50 $\mu\text{g/l}$, where the
196 percentage with high COV decreased from 100 to 50%. Even at TP $> 200 \mu\text{g/l}$, 20-40% (average 26%) of the
197 lakes still had a COV $> 20\%$ and, on average, 54% a COV $> 1\%$. Submerged macrophytes were present (COV
198 $> 1\%$) in all lakes with TP $< 20 \mu\text{g/l}$ and in 94% of the lakes with TP $< 50 \mu\text{g/l}$. Submerged macrophytes were
199 still found in about 50% of the shallow lakes at TP $> 400 \mu\text{g/l}$. In lakes with mean depth < 3 m and at TP
200 concentrations $> 0.2 \text{ mg/l}$, lakes with COV $< 1\%$ as a mean had a significantly lower area, higher mean and
201 maximum depths, higher conductivity, lower Secchi depth and higher Chla than lakes with COV $> 20\%$
202 (Table 3). TP and TN did not differ significantly between lakes with high and low COV at high TP.

203 204 **Discussion**

205 Our results underline the significant negative impact that eutrophication has on submerged macrophytes in
206 shallow lakes (Phillips et al., 2016). At increasing Chla and decreased Secchi depth, the two abundance
207 indicators, COV and PVI, both decreased. The response to eutrophication was hierarchical – nutrients
208 impacted Chla, and Chla causes turbidity and thereby COV and PVI. The direct effect of nutrients on
209 macrophyte abundance was nearly absent and mediated through water clarity (Chla/Secchi depth) with
210 additional interactive effects of alkalinity, mean depth and colour. Chla, on the other hand, was predicted
211 to a high degree by nutrient concentrations, where nitrogen was almost as important as phosphorus and
212 with some effects of COV and alkalinity. The high importance of nitrogen on Chla and then subsequently on
213 macrophyte abundance, suggest that lake managers should not only focus on phosphorus loading
214 reductions, but also nitrogen loading in order to improve the ecological quality of lakes and their
215 biodiversity, as also concluded in other studies (e.g. Barker et al., 2008; Olsen et al., 2015; Søndergaard et
216 al., 2017).

217
218 The multiple regression analyses also suggest that turbidity- and eutrophication-related factors, Chla and
219 Secchi depth, were important factors having the highest explanatory power for the submerged macrophyte
220 community in shallow lakes. For all three macrophyte indicators, however, lake area and/or depth were
221 also important. The empirical relationship using Chla, Secchi depth and mean depth as the three main
222 predictors of COV, as found by the BRT analyses, however, only explained 32% of the variability in COV.
223 Use of the regression models to estimate target concentrations of Chla and nutrients to obtain a certain
224 COV and ecological quality is therefore more uncertain than the BRT models.

225
226 For most predictors, their effect on macrophyte abundance changed considerably and often non-linearly
227 along a eutrophication gradient in the BRT analyses, for Chla and TP particularly at low concentrations. For
228 example, the effects of Chla on COV and PVI were marked at Chla below ca. 50 $\mu\text{g/l}$, after which a further
229 increase in Chla did not affect the fitted function. Similarly, Chla was particularly affected at TP up to ca. 0.2
230 mg/l , whereas a gradual response was found for TN, supporting the general perception that both
231 phosphorus and nitrogen can be important limiting factors for phytoplankton growth (Seip, 1994; Barker et
232 al., 2008; Olsen et al., 2015; Liang et al., 2020) and that the individual importance of the two nutrients
233 varies with concentration levels and seasons (Søndergaard et al., 2017a). The inadequacy of phosphorus as
234 a predictor of macrophyte abundance, particularly at high TP as seen in the BRT-analyses, was also
235 illustrated by the presence of macrophytes in almost half of the shallow lakes with TP $> 0.2 \text{ mg TP/l}$ and the

236 fact that COV even exceeded 20% as an average in 26% of these lakes. The BRT analyses also revealed a
237 unique cover effect on Chla up to a COV of about 40%, where COV was the third most important predictor
238 after TP and TN. This allows quantification of the relative importance of plant-related feedback effects of
239 cover in reducing Chla independent of nutrients. Thereby, it feeds into the discussion of at which level of
240 COV, a major impact on the overall biological structure in shallow lakes, including Chla, can be anticipated
241 (Canfield 1983; Wang et al., 2014; Gao et al., 2020). The effect of increasing COV on Chla was gradual up to
242 40% COV, and the existence of a COV threshold, as indicated earlier, is therefore not supported
243 (Søndergaard et al., 2016). Any increase in COV up to 30-40% could be a target for lake managers in order
244 to create more clear water in shallow lakes, whereas a higher COV would not have any further impact on
245 Chla. High COV in shallow lakes has been associated with reduced conditions close to the sediment which
246 can impact the biogeochemical nutrient cycling and lead to increased internal phosphorus release (Stephen
247 et al., 1997; Boros et al. 2011; Waters & Webster-Brown, 2020).

248
249 Species richness (taxa number) depends on different factors in different regions of the world (Alahuhta et
250 al., 2017), but here we found that area was the most important, with effects mainly up to around 100 ha.
251 The inclusion of lakes down to 1 ha in this study probably amplifies the area effect on species richness
252 compared to other studies analysing large lakes only. Alkalinity was the second-most important factor with
253 a maximum effect on species richness around 1 meq/l and with a decreasing effect up to around 4 meq/l.
254 This optimum may reflect that species richness is higher in lakes with high than low alkalinity and that
255 intermediate alkalinity from ca. 0.2 to 1 meq/l allows co-occurrence of elodeids and isoetids (Vestergaard &
256 Sand-Jensen 2000; Søndergaard et al., 2020). The eutrophication indicators, Chla, TP and Secchi depth, also
257 added significantly to the total variance of taxa number explained, but they contributed much less than
258 area and alkalinity. Our analyses could therefore not confirm that vertical expansion was higher than
259 horizontal expansion and thereby that high Secchi depth increased species richness more than lake area
260 (Vestergaard & Sand-Jensen; 2000). Colour had only a minor effect on species richness, but the number of
261 highly coloured lakes in our study was small, implying that potential colour effects and shading by dissolved
262 organic carbon on macrophyte communities cannot be ruled out (Reitsema et al., 2020).

263
264 There are several potential caveats in our study. Firstly, we focused on physical and chemical factors for
265 predicting macrophyte communities despite the numerous interactions with other biological components.
266 As effects of chlorophyll and the cover feedback on chlorophyll are included in the analyses, and as the
267 BRTs explain a large amount of variance, we do not expect that these caveats have great importance for
268 the overall picture. Secondly, we do not know to which extent the lakes included in the analyses represent
269 lakes in equilibrium. Some of them may still be in recovery after changed environmental conditions (Kozak
270 & Goldyn, 2016; Søndergaard et al., 2017b) or the expansion of macrophytes may not immediately follow
271 changes in abiotic conditions, as also the occurrence of propagules, herbivory and plant competition may
272 play a role (Baker et al., 2012). Moreover, for macrophytes, there may be a carryover effect from previous
273 years as opposed to phytoplankton biomass for which there is little "memory" from year to year (Rooney &
274 Kalff, 2000; Cobbaert et al., 2014). Thirdly, in the search for nutrient-macrophyte interactions it may be
275 difficult to discriminate between causes and consequences, since the presence of submerged macrophytes
276 has significant effects on the internal nutrient cycling (Dai et al., 2015; Søndergaard et al., 2017b; Li et al.,
277 2020). These effects may differ depending on which species dominate; meadow-forming species have
278 strong effects on turbidity and reduce nutrient concentrations, whereas canopy-forming species are less
279 significant in controlling the internal nutrient cycling (Gao et al., 2020). Finally, differences in the winter
280 survival of macrophytes, timing of the spring clear-water phase, local weather conditions during winter and
281 spring and a number of biological interactions are all factors that can add to the variability in macrophyte
282 abundance (Jeppesen et al., 1998; Mämetts et al., 2006; Phillips et al., 2016), but data were not available in
283 this study to further evaluate their importance. Again, the large predictive power of the BRT analyses
284 suggest that this is not a serious problem for the general conclusions.

285

286 Overall, the effect of eutrophication on the macrophyte indicators was hierarchical and primarily depended
287 on water clarity (Chla/Secchi depth) interacting with alkalinity, depth and area. In contrast, TP and TN were
288 not good predictors, because their effects were mediated through water clarity with interactions of area,
289 mean depth, colour and alkalinity. The Chla concentration was highly predictable based on nutrient
290 concentrations but limited to a rather short TP range (up to 0.2 mg/l), whereas the TN effect was much
291 more stable across the length of the gradient. For lake managers the gradual changes in impact of different
292 nutrients and environmental factors may be used to develop lake specific management plans.

293

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304

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313

314 Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

315 No conflict of interest.

316 Availability of data and material

317 The data sets generated during and/or analysed in the current study are available from the corresponding
318 author upon reasonable request.

319

320 Code availability

321 Not applicable.

322

323 Authors' contributions

324 Material preparation and data analysis were performed by Martin Søndergaard, Thomas Davidson and
325 Liselotte S. Johansson. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Martin Søndergaard and all authors
326 commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

327

328 Ethics approval

329 Ethical Responsibilities approved by authors.

330

331 Consent to participate

332 Not applicable.

333

334 Consent for publication

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538 **Table captions**

539

540 Table 1. Morphometric and chemical characteristics and macrophyte data on the lakes (lake years) included in this
541 study represented by mean, minimum, 10% percentile, 25% percentile, median, 75% percentile, 90% percentile and
542 maximum values. TA: total alkalinity, TP: total phosphorus, TN: total nitrogen, Chla: chlorophyll α , COV: coverage of
543 submerged macrophytes, PVI: plant volume inhabited.

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546 Table 2. Multiple regressions between taxa number, COV and PVI as dependent variables and \log_{10} of the variables
547 mentioned in Table 1. In all regressions and for all variables, p was <0.0001. Only variables where partial R-square >
548 0.01 are shown.

549

550 Table 3. Mean physical and chemical values for lakes with mean depth < 3 m and summer mean TP > 0.2 mg/l shown
551 for lakes with COV \leq 1% and lakes with COV > 20%. Significant differences (t-test) between the two means are shown
552 in the right column with significance levels: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, - = not significant.

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556 **Tables**
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Table 1.

Variable	Number of lake years	Mean	Min.	10%	25%	Median	75%	90%	Max.
Area (ha)	1447	55.3	1.0	3.0	6.4	14.7	43.8	134	1713
Mean depth (m)	1446	1.2	0.03	0.38	0.66	1.1	1.7	2.3	3.0
Max depth (m)	1447	2.7	0.04	0.90	1.40	2.1	3.5	5.5	10.1
TA (meq/l)	1438	2.24	-0.07	0.14	1.15	2.24	3.19	4.00	10.1
Colour (mg Pt/l)	1293	60	0	17	25	38	61	117	1001
Conductivity (mS/m)	1324	266	0.7	15	27	42	72	945	7568
Secchi depth (m)	1431	1.03	0.08	0.37	0.56	0.84	1.29	1.85	6.13
TP (mg/l)	1352	0.224	0.004	0.034	0.061	0.112	0.220	0.461	6.31
TN (mg/l)	1353	1.73	0.27	0.70	0.94	1.38	2.00	3.09	51.0
Chla (µg/l)	1442	63	0.0	7.2	15.6	40.1	83.4	141	1199
COV (%)	1447	22.0	0	0	0.6	10.7	37.9	62.7	97.5
PVI (%)	1327	10.6	0	0	0.1	2.9	14.5	34.0	89.3
Taxa no.	1336	7.4	0	0	2	5	11	17	53

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562 Table 2.

Dependent variable	N	Intercept	Variable entered	Parameter estimate	Partial R-square	Model R-square
Taxa no.	1182	8.39	Log ₁₀ area	6.11	0.17	0.17
			Log ₁₀ Chla	-4.52	0.14	0.31
			Log ₁₀ colour	3.99	0.03	0.34
			Log ₁₀ TP	-3.67	0.03	0.36
COV	1424	42.4	Log ₁₀ Chla	-15.6	0.26	0.26
			Log ₁₀ mean depth	- 31.3	0.02	0.28
			Log ₁₀ Secchi depth	32.1	0.04	0.32
			Log ₁₀ area	4.77	0.01	0.34
PVI	1279	22.9	Log ₁₀ Chla	-7.97	0.12	0.12
			Log ₁₀ mean depth	- 19.2	0.08	0.20
			Log ₁₀ Secchi depth	10.8	0.01	0.21
			Log ₁₀ alkalinity	2.92	0.01	0.22

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Table 3.

Variable	COV =< 1%		COV > 20%		Difference
	Mean	N	Mean	N	
Area (ha)	20.4	181	97.1	102	***
Mean depth (m)	1.15	180	0.73	102	***
Max depth (m)	2.35	181	1.59	102	***
TA (meq/l)	3.23	180	3.17	102	-
Colour (mg Pt/l)	62.5	160	72.3	93	-
Conductivity (mS/m)	274	157	645	99	**
Secchi depth (m)	0.62	181	0.78	101	**
TP (mg/l)	0.65	181	0.50	102	-
TN (mg/l)	2.92	181	2.29	102	-
Chla ($\mu\text{g/l}$)	149	181	66.7	102	***

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569 **Figure captions**

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573 Fig. 1. Partial dependence plots of the boosted regression tree analyses for the four most influential predictor
574 variables. The analyses were conducted for lakes with a mean depth < 3 m and included the three macrophyte
575 indicators shown from above: taxa numbers, COV and PVI and Chla (the lower figure). The plots show the fitted
576 function (solid line) and the smooth function (dashed line) relative to the predictor variables, all other predictor
577 variables being averaged out. The left part of the figure shows the total variance explained and the relative influence
578 of the predictor.

579

580 Fig. 2. As Fig. 1 but shows the analyses of COV including only data with Chla < 200 µg/l and the analyses of Chla
581 including only data with TP < 2 mg/l.

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583 Fig. 3. Percentage of lake year observations with COV above 1% (blue line) and above 20% (red line) at increasing TP
584 concentrations. Only lakes with mean depth < 3 m (number of lake years = 1351) are included. The blue line with COV
585 > 1% also includes lake years with COV > 20% (red line).

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Figures

Fig. 1.

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Fig. 2.

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Fig. 3.

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